

ПРИЛОЖЕНИЕ 2.

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//SEVERA2 JOB MSGLEVEL=(1,1)
// EXEC FORTGCLG
// FORT.SYSIN DD *
DIMENSION BCOFR(16),BCOFI(16),ACOFR(16,16),
,ACOFI(16,16),NA(16,16),B(32)
COMPLEX DE,ZS,ZU,A(35),B1(16),AI(36)
EQUIVALENCE(B(1),B1(1))
DATA NA/1,5,8,5,20,8,5,20,20,20,8,5,20,20,20,20,
,2,5,9,12,20,18,12,20,20,20,18,12,20,20,20,20,
,3,15,10,20,5,10,20,20,20,20,10,20,20,20,20,
,4,25,11,16,12,19,20,20,20,13,19,20,20,20,20,20,
,2,5,18,12,20,21,22,20,20,20,30,22,20,20,20,20,
,3,6,10,13,13,10,13,20,20,15,10,13,5,20,20,13,
,4,26,19,5,22,9,16,20,13,10,18,20,20,20,20,20,
,4,4,11,4,10,19,10,20,16,25,19,10,20,20,13,10,
,4,2,19,8,8,9,2,16,5,29,18,8,20,13,10,8,
,2,5,18,12,20,30,22,20,20,20,31,33,20,20,20,20,
,4,27,19,12,33,18,5,13,10,8,32,16,20,20,20,20,
,4,3,19,4,16,18,4,35,28,12,32,3,5,20,13,13,
,4,15,10,20,20,10,20,20,20,15,10,20,20,20,15,5,
,4,16,11,16,20,19,20,20,16,16,19,20,20,16,25,12,
,4,16,19,20,20,9,16,16,20,20,18,20,35,28,12,34,
,4,15,19,16,16,18,16,35,35,20,32,15,7,5,26,22/
READ(5,201) NN
500 CONTINUE
READ(5,101) DE,ZS,ZU
WRITE(6,102) DE,ZS,ZU
101 FORMAT(6F7.3)
102 FORMAT(2X,'DE=',2F7.3,'ZS=',2F7.3,'ZU=',2F7.3)
A(1)=3*ZS+2*ZU
A(2)=3*ZS+ZU
A(3)=2*ZS+2*ZU
A(4)=2*ZS+ZU
A(5)=-ZS
A(6)=ZS+2*ZU
A(7)=ZS+ZU
A(8)=3*ZS
A(9)=6*ZS+ZU
A(10)=2*ZS
A(11)=4*ZS+ZU
A(12)=-2*ZS
A(13)=ZS
A(14)=3*ZS+ZU
A(15)=2*ZU
A(16)=ZU
A(17)=ZS+4*ZU
A(18)=6*ZS
A(19)=4*ZS
A(20)=0
A(21)=9*ZS+ZU
A(22)=-3*ZS
A(23)=-2*ZU
A(24)=ZS-ZU
A(25)=-ZS+ZU
A(26)=-2*ZS+ZU
A(27)=-3*ZS+ZU
A(28)=-ZS-ZU
A(29)=-2*ZS-ZU
A(30)=9*ZS
A(31)=12*ZS+ZU
A(32)=8*ZS+ZU
A(33)=-4*ZS

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A(30)=9*Z5
A(31)=12*Z5+ZU
A(32)=8*Z5+ZU
A(33)=-4*Z5
A(34)=-3*Z5-ZU
A(35)=-ZU
DC 100 I=1,16
BCOFR(1)=REAL(DE)
BCOFI(1)=AIMAG(DE)
DC 100 J=1,16
K=NA(J,1)
ACOFR(1,J)=REAL(A(K))
ACOFI(1,J)=AIMAG(A(K))
100 CONTINUE
CALL CGAUS(BCOFR,BCOFI,ACOFR,ACOFI,16,1)
DC 110 I=1,16
B(2*I-1)=BCOFR(I)
B(2*I)=BCOFI(I)
110 CONTINUE
AI(1)=2*(B1(1)+B1(3)+B1(6)+B1(11))
AI(2)=B1(1)
AI(3)=B1(1)-B1(2)+B1(3)-B1(4)+B1(6)-B1(7)+B1(11)-B1(12)
AI(4)=B1(2)
AI(5)=2*(B1(3)+B1(6)+B1(11))
AI(6)=B1(3)
AI(7)=-B1(3)+B1(4)-B1(6)+B1(7)-B1(11)+B1(12)
AI(8)=B1(4)
AI(9)=-B1(2)-B1(5)+B1(10)
AI(10)=B1(5)
AI(11)=2*(B1(6)+B1(11))
AI(12)=B1(6)
AI(13)=B1(7)-B1(6)-B1(11)+B1(12)
AI(14)=B1(7)
AI(15)=B1(2)+B1(4)+B1(5)-B1(9)-B1(10)
AI(16)=B1(8)
AI(17)=B1(2)+B1(4)+B1(5)+B1(7)+B1(16)+B1(15)-B1(9)-B1(10)+
+B1(12)+B1(14)
AI(18)=B1(9)
AI(19)=-B1(10)+B1(2)+B1(4)+B1(7)+B1(5)+B1(12)+B1(15)+B1(16)
AI(20)=B1(10)
AI(21)=-B1(2)-B1(4)-B1(5)-B1(7)-B1(12)-B1(16)
AI(22)=B1(11)
AI(23)=2*B1(11)
AI(24)=B1(12)
AI(25)=B1(12)-B1(11)
AI(26)=B1(12)+B1(2)+B1(4)+B1(5)+B1(7)-B1(8)-B1(9)-B1(10)
AI(27)=B1(7)-B1(8)+B1(4)-B1(9)+B1(2)+B1(5)-B1(10)
AI(28)=B1(13)
AI(29)=B1(2)+B1(4)+B1(5)+B1(7)-B1(8)-B1(9)-B1(10)+B1(12)-B1(13)
AI(30)=-B1(13)-B1(14)-B1(15)-B1(16)
AI(31)=B1(13)
AI(32)=B1(14)
AI(33)=-B1(14)-B1(15)-B1(16)
AI(34)=B1(15)
AI(35)=-B1(15)-B1(16)
AI(36)=B1(16)
WRITE(6,200)
200 FORMAT(2X,' RE IM')
DC 150 I=1,36
150 WRITE(6,201) I,AI(I)
201 FORMAT(I3,2F10.3)
NN=NN-1
IF(NN.GT.0) GO TO 500
STOP
END

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